

A DISCOURSE ANALYSIS ON BUSINESS PLAN EXECUTIVE SUMMARIES: RHETORIC STRUCTURE IN FOCUS

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A Discourse Analysis on Business Plan Executive Summaries: Rhetoric Structure in Focus

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Abstract

A well-written executive summary speaks for the quality of the report- it reflects the value of the document. The business plan is a relatively organized entrepreneurial endeavor and implements activities for the success of the business venture, thus, the writing of an executive summary can be problematic and challenging. Anchored on Hyland's (2000) five-move model, a corpus of twenty-one (21) randomly selected business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019-2022. The results demonstrated that the move structure employed in writing business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019-2022 are namely Introduction- Purpose- Method- Product- Conclusion moves. It was noted that these are the move structures that have been followed and employed by the writers. Furthermore, the findings also revealed that there are three dominant move structures observed in the corpus of business plan executive summaries namely Introduction- Purpose- Method- Product- Conclusion, Introduction-Method- Product- Conclusion, and Introduction- Purpose- Method- Product. It was also noted that the "Purpose" and "Conclusion" moves have sometimes been not observed or have been omit by the writer. Additionally, it was advised that business plan instructors in business administration follow a certain pattern in writing their executive summary to make students who write the summary familiar with the structure and vital components of a well-written document. Through this, writers will be inspired to produce a more coherent summary.

Keywords: *discourse analysis, business plan, executive summary, move structure*

Introduction

A well-crafted business plan is essential for the success of any business, and at the heart of this plan is an effective executive summary. This section describes the business outlines the problem or issues it aims to solve, presents the identified audience, and highlights key financial considerations. However, there are common mistakes encountered in terms of structure such as making the executive summary overly lengthy, failing to engage the reader, and allowing typos, grammatical errors, or poor formatting to slip through are observed enemies in crafting an executive summary (Lake, 2020).

In the international setting, students writing business plans commonly face similar challenges to small business owners, particularly when crafting an executive summary, and it is noticed by a Small Business Development Center in Rhode Island. However, common mistakes often arise specifically having a not short, having no clear points, and without deep background in the case of a business. These mistakes can hinder the overall impact of a business plan, especially when made by students who may be less experienced in business writing. It needs to avoid writing an executive summary to stay on the right path improve the plan and take the next step toward business success (Daly, 2019).

In the Philippines, errors in writing a business plan executive summary are manifested by the students in Business Administration of Pangasinan State University in San Carlos, Pangasinan. Common mistakes observed are unclear objectives which the failure to clearly state what the business intends to achieve including the goal and objectives, overly lengthy summaries that many students produced containing excessive detail which it intended to be brief and concise, unnecessary details that students often included irrelevant information to the executive summary, and excessive use of grammar or punctuation, included overly complex sentence structures, overuse or misuse of commas or periods, and incorrect punctuation. Furthermore, they are trying to identify factors that are potentially associated with students' susceptibility to commit errors in composing a business plan executive summary (Flora et.al, 2019).

From the previous paragraphs, the discourse analysis on business plan executive summaries has brought concern and problems to the institution. In this regard, this study has extensive social significance as this can be a scholarly basis for the progress of business plan executive summary writing among students in business administration. By identifying the common errors and challenges students face in crafting these summaries, the study can serve as a foundation for improving writing instruction within the institution. In that way, it enhances the overall quality of education, ensuring that graduates possess the practical skills required in real-world business environments. Furthermore, this study is urgent since crafting an executive summary of the business plan is part of the academic requirements in the institution, and there are no sufficient studies that have been produced to examine the lapses. By conducting this study, the researcher can provide valuable insights that can help to close this gap and contribute to the field of business communication. Given the importance of business plan writing in academic settings and the professional world, addressing these issues promptly is essential for preparing students to meet the expectations of both academia and industry. Thus, the researcher wants to study discourse analysis with a business plan executive summary to contribute to fundamental research. Through this, relevant and effective writing can be practiced as this proposal can benefit them to assess their outputs to gear the students in writing an executive summary of a business plan. Thus, all of these premises prompt me to propose and focus on this study.

Despite the mentioned studies, it has been rarely used to analyze the rhetorical move structure of business plan executive summary.

Other previous studies encompass the grammar knowledge and vocabulary mastery of business management students in English. A study conducted by Jitpanich et al. (2022) entitled “English for Business Management Students: Need Analysis in English for Specific Purposes”. In the said study they focus on the student needs in language proficiency skills which are related to business plan writing. Another study conducted by Flora (2019) entitled “Grammatical Errors in the Business Correspondence Corpora of Sophomore BSBA Students” focuses on ensuring factors potentially connected to the susceptibility of students to commit grammatical errors in the composition of their business correspondence. Another study conducted by Yutthasak (2022) entitled “The Problems of Summary Writing Encountered by Thai EFL Students: A Case Study of the Fourth Year English Major Students at Naresuan University” found that it was difficult to locate the central ideas of the text and there are chances to lost focus about summary writing. This study also focuses on the difficulty encountered by the students in paraphrasing and revising a summary. Although these studies had yielded promising results, none of them have come across a study that specifically conducts the discourse analysis on business plan executive summaries. Moreover, this study provides relevant concepts that will possibly contribute to the social and academic community. This, therefore, establishes the research gap of the study.

Research Questions

This research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the rhetorical move structure employed in writing business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019-2022?
2. What are the common structures found in business plan executive summaries from the year 2019-2022?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized qualitative research design in a discourse analysis approach. I used a qualitative research format since the goal of this study was to unmask the rhetorical structure of a business plan executive summaries. Qualitative research is an inquiry approach that is useful for exploring and understanding a central phenomenon. Moreover, qualitative research collects and works with non-numerical data and seeks to interpret meaning (Crossman, 2020).

In this study, the discourse analysis method is suitable because it focuses on using and gathering information from business plan executive summaries in the years 2019-2022. As a result, the rhetorical move structure employed, and the common structure found in the business plan executive summaries from the business administration students were thoroughly examined and analyzed through the discourse analysis method for enhanced comprehension and to prevent inaccurate interpretation.

Discourse analysis also known as discourse studies, refers to a variety of techniques for examining spoken, written, sign language, or any other significant semiotic event. Consistent patterns of sentences, propositions, or speech are variously defined as the objects of discourse analysis, including discourse writing, conversation, and communicative events. Furthermore, it aims to understand how language is used in real-life situations. It is an interpretative method of analyzing texts in which the researcher makes interpretations based on both the details of the material itself and contextual knowledge. Moreover, the discourse analysis context may include a social and cultural framework, including the location of a speaker at the time of the discourse, as well as nonverbal cues, images, and symbols, and focus on the types of language cultural rules, and conversations, how values, beliefs and assumptions are communicated and how language use relates to its social, political, and historical context (Johnstone, 2018).

In context, this study aims to identify the move structures used of such materials which are the business plan executive summaries. Moreover, this inquiry also aims to determine the common structures present in the executive summaries through examination of the written materials. These were achieved by gathering data and collecting materials in the school library that served as corpora in the inquiry.

Instrument

The corpora that the researcher has utilized in this study are the business plan executive summaries. The business plan, particularly the executive summary section, was the source of data in this research wherein the rhetorical move structures and common structures can be found.

The research materials that have been used in this study are the 21-business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019-2022. The basis of the number of corpora to be used was the accessibility of the executive summaries being created because the business plan executive summaries have things that also need to be addressed. This implies that the creators of any executive summaries have a better vision, and actions should be taken to make it happen. Braun and Clarke (2013) provided suggestions on the number of research materials to focus on. As anchored, it has previously been recommended that this study requires a minimum sample size of at least 10-100 research materials as sources to sufficiently fulfill the goal of the study and reach data saturation. Therefore, 21 executive summaries are deemed sufficient for this study to be undertaken.

Specifically, the executive summary of the business plan that this study utilized is those outputs solely of the business administration

students. These summaries are chosen by using the following selection criteria: (1) must be an executive summary found in the business plan in the year 2019-2022, (2) must have an introduction, purpose, methods, results, and conclusion, and (3) executive summaries that are available and accessible in the library. Since this study utilized a corpus, the researcher was only gathering the materials needed. The corpora were named BPES-01 and followed, till reached BPES-51.

To protect the identity of the people, mentioned in the material, I followed the ethical principles of anonymization, etc. found and recommended in the humanities and social sciences for research in Sweden (Hogan, 2015). To add relevant information, principles on anonymization identify variables that include direct identifiers, which include names, addresses, or identity card numbers. These variables enable the direct identification of respondents but are unnecessary for statistical or research purposes and should therefore be excluded from the published dataset.

Procedure

As a researcher, I took a series of steps in collecting data and other viable information relevant to the study. Before conducting the study, I coordinated with my adviser to know how I was going to start the research study and what steps that are needed to be taken to accomplish this research. As this is a corpus-based discourse analysis, the researcher coordinated with the head librarian and presented its signed permission letter to allow the researcher to access the corpora needed which was the executive summary of the business plan found in the business plan outputs in the years 2019-2022. The researcher now accessed the material needed; the researcher secured a photocopy of each executive summary.

To start the data collection, a manuscript has been proposed to the research technical panel for a thorough review. Once approved by the panel members, the pilot collection of the needed executive summaries of each business plan found in the academic year 2019-2022. These summaries are chosen by using the following selection criteria: (1) must be an executive summary found in the business plan in the years 2019, 2020, 2021, and 2022, (2) must have an introduction, purpose, methods, results, and conclusion, and (3) executive summaries that are available and accessible in the library. The corpora are the executive summaries created by the students in the Business Administration Program. The corpora were named BPES-01 and followed, till reached BPES-51.

The documents helped me in gaining a clear vision of the discourse analysis on executive summaries. The data collected are subject to treatment and interpretation. Relevant information has been presented in the following chapters to have a vivid view of the research that it undergoes. The results have been presented and discussed. The information has been analyzed, explored, and treated based on the problems of the study.

Data Analysis

The corpora that have been used in this study were the 21-business plan executive summaries from the academic year 2019-2022. Corpora has been utilized in this study to have a large collection of real-life language used in the executive summaries and to ensure the reliability of information gathered from the corpora. Thus, this study utilizes qualitative research design in a discourse analysis approach.

Additionally, qualitative analysis involves systematically organizing and processing data by managing, synthesizing, and examining it for patterns. This process includes identifying key insights, determining their significance, and extracting meaningful conclusions. As a result, it requires a thorough examination of the raw data and an understanding of the logical relationships within the identified categories.

Aside from that, both first and second research questions have been answered by the Hyland (2000) five-move model. The framework aided the researcher in providing the rhetorical move structure employed and aided the common structures found in business plan executive summaries from the year 2019-2022.

Furthermore, this study compiled the move structures found in the executive summary of the business plan. These summaries are chosen with a selection criterion to ensure their appropriateness as research materials for this study. The material must be an executive summary found in business plans in the years 2019-2022 and must have an introduction, purpose, methods, results, and conclusion, and executive summaries that are available and accessible in the library. These executive summaries have been coded with PC.

The corpora are the executive summaries created by the students in the Business Administration Program. The corpora are named BPES-01 and followed, till they reach BPES-51. Business plan executive summaries possess a rhetorical move structure because the writers of the said report use moves to achieve the communicative purposes of the text.

Ethical Considerations

To uphold ethical standards in scientific research, ethical principles were prioritized and carefully applied throughout the conduct of this study. I adhered to the following ethical guidelines: respect for individuals, beneficence, and justice (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for Persons requires that researchers avoid taking advantage of any vulnerabilities among participants. Maintaining humility is essential to fostering trust, confidence, and positive relationships with those involved, including the creators of policies or guidelines (Creswell, 2012). Before starting the study, I sought permission from the school library by sending a formal request. This step was

taken to demonstrate respect for all individuals involved in the research.

To ensure that a person's rights have been protected qualitative research needs to adhere to some criteria to maintain their ethicality. Regarding this inquiry, there was a permission letter needed because the corpora that have been utilized are from the business plan output of the business administration students.

Moreover, the appropriateness of research methodology has been utilized to ensure that qualitative research follows its main objectives. The design of the research was appropriate to obtain merit to continue in this inquiry. The full reporting of the methods that were employed in this study was significantly vital and made the data reliable and credible.

Beneficence requires a commitment to minimizing risks to the research participants who are recognized in this study as the provider of the document needed for this study while maximizing the profits that are due to them (Bricki & Green, 2007). The anonymity of the creator of the report was kept in order not to put each of them at risk. Persons involved and parties were been censored to protect their identities. At all times, every file of information gathered was not left unattended or unprotected. On a positive note, this study introduces valuable concepts that may benefit both the social and academic communities by enhancing their awareness of existing executive summaries. This could lead to a clearer understanding of business plan executive summaries. Additionally, the study seeks to foster a comprehensive awareness of these summaries among students.

In addressing issues in beneficence, I explained the risk, the process, and the objectives of the study to the designated person/s. I also emphasized that they would also benefit from the result of the study by using it as their point of reference or set of guidelines in crafting business plan executive summaries following the structure of it. I made sure to maximize the benefit while minimizing the risk to ensure that the beneficiaries as well as the involved parties benefit greatly from this study.

Justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as part of the results of the research (Crabtree & Bloom, 2006). In this study, justice was achieved by utilizing appropriate methods of research, analysis, and presentation of data. Moreover, the researcher ensured that confidentiality in the documents was highly maintained to avoid harming the people involved in the study.

Furthermore, to ensure ethical consideration in this research, I removed and covered the names of the students or the names of the businesses involved in the business plan executive summaries that have been used in the study. Further, I gave full attention to protecting the good name of the institution and stakeholders involved in the conduct of the study. Additionally, accurate information has been explained and Made clear to the readers so that they can understand the very purpose and nature of this study.

Moreover, it was essential to recognize the contributions of all participants, as they played a vital role in the success of the research. Their efforts should be acknowledged and properly credited in all aspects of the study. Lastly, the researcher exercised language that was politically aware and correct to maintain the desired extent of objectivity in the study.

Consent and Confidentiality require the protection of confidential data, communications, records, and other documents and it should not be done without permission. Confidentiality was required to obtain informed consent and build trust with participants. During data cleaning, confidentiality addresses create a "clean" data set, as a researcher (Crow et al., 2006).

Further, to get permission, I ensured to have a letter of consent first to the office involved in my research. Also, to protect the identities of people mentioned in the data, I did not include the names of the business, and I kept the data private to ensure privacy and safety, and to ensure that the data that had been gathered was permitted, reliable, and accurate.

Despite the research materials that I utilized in this inquiry being from the library can be accessed easily, I gave the assurance that the confidentiality of the identity of each corpus was still in the utmost secured and preserved. The executive summaries that are included in this study are given a code to ensure anonymity. The data processing appropriately handles that only the researcher, adviser, and expert panel will have access to the extent of this inquiry.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the gathered data taken from business plan executive summaries. The summaries were analyzed to identify the rhetoric move structures employed in the academic year 2019-2022. The data was collected to answer the two research questions; first, what is the move structure employed in writing business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019-2022? Second, what are the common structures found in business plan executive summaries from the year 2019-2022? This part of the paper presented the rhetoric move structure. The analysis was made by the researcher on the business plan executive summary, and it was found that it has structures employed. The data collected were analyzed based on Hyland's five-move model.

Research Question 1: What is the rhetorical move structure employed in writing business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019 - 2022?

A rhetorical move structure refers to the strategic actions a writer takes to achieve a coherent communicative function in written or spoken discourse. Each move carries a specific communicative purpose and, when combined with other moves, contributes to the overall goal of the text. Following the pattern in writing an executive summary enables the writers to achieve the aims of the summary.

The analysis was made by the researcher on the Business plan Executive Summaries and it was found out that it has rhetorical move structures followed by the writers. The data collected were analyzed based on Hyland's Five Move Model.

A rhetorical move structure focuses on how the writer used a move such as the introduction, purpose, method, product, and conclusion enable achieve a certain communicative purpose of a text. The move structure in a business plan executive summary was analyzed in a tabular presentation which points out the move pattern in writing an executive summary.

The rhetorical move structure has been used by the researcher as it seems to address the same purpose of informing the readers about the pieces of information in the summary. Indeed, the introduction move in the Hyland model should provide information about the context of the executive summary generate background of the business plan, and motivate the summary. The purpose move is the vital move where the writer of the summary indicates the main purpose of the plan and summarizes the objective behind the business report. This move is undoubtedly the most significant one in an executive summary since all other moves in the executive summary are dependent on the main aim of the plan. It should reveal the interest and the aims of the content of the summary. The method is the third move which covers information about the company overview, the marketing, operations, financial, and management team plan, and the data collection and analysis tools. It should claim the procedures and describe the materials, steps, or subjects. The product, which is the fourth move in the model. The writer or the proponents reports about the data examined, and highlights and summarizes the noteworthy findings. The result shows the distribution of this important move through the data and reporting the findings concisely. The last move in executive summary writing is the conclusion which refers to the findings beyond the scope of the report, shows points to applications, and implications, and presents recommendations.

For better understanding, presented in Table 1 is the move structure employed in writing business plan executive summaries for the academic year 2019-2022 that is analyzed according to its move and sample statement from the corpora. The first column exudes the move structure such as the introduction, purpose, method, product, and conclusion. Further, the sample statement illustrates the accounts written by its writers or proponents where the move patterns have been found.

Table 1. Move Structure employed in Writing Business Plan Executive Summaries in the Academic Year 2019-2022

<i>Move</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Introduction	<p>“This printing service or printing shop will focus on reducing a printing price structure, for printing presses and graphic art design. It derives on giving a service to students who need a quality and trustworthy printing shop and will offer services not available in the market...” - BPES-02</p> <p>“This salon business offers hair rebond, hair color, make-up, and nail spas in the market. The business will be located at Brgy Gabuyan, Kapalong, davao del Norte...” - BPES-03</p> <p>“It is a store that offers crisp and succulent with moist and tasty meat roasted suckling pig that easily falls off the bones and will provide satisfaction to the needs of the consumers at affordable prices...” - BPES-04</p> <p>“This product produces baked brownies that are nutritious, fudge, and delicious for everyone. Customers can choose brownies from a variety of flavors and categories. These brownies are not just ordinary brownies from other stores because the customer can choose between regular and low-carb brownies...” - BPES-09</p> <p>“The first ever coffee shop with mini library in the municipality of Kapalong. It serves various kinds of hot and cold drinks such as coffees, lattes, tea, milk, and smoothies. Also, it will be available for dine-in and take-out orders...” -BPES-07</p>
Purpose	<p>“The business aims to provide food that has premium quality to ensure customer satisfaction. The product has a twist and innovation, and the pricing to compete in the market...” - BPES-01</p> <p>“The salon aims to be a number one salon in the locality and wants to provide job opportunities to the people who are skilled and willing to work...” - BPES-03</p> <p>“This business envisions offering quality and affordable gas service with facilities and systems powered by advanced technology. And, its goals and objectives of this business is to provide an excellent service to the valued customers...” - BPES-05</p> <p>“The brownies product aspires to promote top-quality taste to individuals. It aims to provide its vision and communication to customers to exceed their expectations and to produce healthy snacks that taste great...” - BPES-09</p> <p>“The business envisions to be a competitive seedling business and a successful provider of seedlings in the Municipality of Kapalong. The goal is to provide good quality seedlings to the potential customers to satisfy their farm needs...” - BPES-10</p>
Method	<p>“As part of the legal obligation, the business will submit all the requirements set by the government to operate the business legally. The business will secure a license to operate for the legitimacy of the business and will have a legal form of ownership as a sole proprietorship type of business...” - BPES-01</p> <p>“To know the internal and external factors that affect the business, a SWOT analysis was made to evaluate business strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, to formulate good and new strategies for the benefit of the business...” - BPES-03</p> <p>“The proponents surveyed questionnaires from establishments and individuals as they would be the future target market the proponents provided good enough consideration on possible variables that could influence the business operations...” - BPES-08</p> <p>“The proponents utilized form-based survey questionnaires to get more detailed information about the potential customers. To determine the market demand of the said areas, 381 individual samples from 7, 916 households were taken using quota sampling...” - BPES-09</p> <p>“The business will use the skimming pricing method in which a firm charges a high initial price and then gradually lowers</p>

	the price to attract more price-sensitive customers. The proponents will use survey questionnaire to determine the pulse of the customers...”- BPES-11
Product	<p>“After the proponents conducted an online survey among the selected respondents of Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The total number of households within the barangay is 3,949 represented by 100 respondents, and it showed that 94% of the respondents prefer to avail the cochinitillo...” - BPES-04</p> <p>“The result shows that the majority of the customers are mostly students and some senior citizens. And according to the survey, 4% of the 1000 respondents have not availed the services and 96% were positive about availing the delivery services...”- BPES-06</p> <p>“The result of the survey positively seen as more consumers and businesses looking for other alternatives to be used for their daily groceries, food, packaging materials, and more. Based on the survey, the data showed the capacity of the target market to avail the products...”- BPES-08</p> <p>“The result shows that 30% of the respondents being surveyed prefer not to avail services from coffee shop business and rather to have their instant coffee at home, while the remaining 70% is the potential market who will avail the business...”- BPES-07</p> <p>“As a result of the survey conducted to over 100 respondents, 96% of them preferred to avail surprises and 4% of them do not want to avail...”- BPES-11</p>
Conclusion	<p>“This business must develop unique styles that provide customers with various ways to create business stationery. Also, the company should develop plans to negotiate deals with big businesses...” - BPES-02</p> <p>“All business transactions should be properly recorded to track the smooth running of business. Good management of financial statements is important in the business to evaluate and measure the performance and stability of the business. The business payback period is 2 years and 1 month...”- BPES-08</p> <p>“After all the computation analysis of the net profit of this Cafe business, the return on investment will be from 4 to 5 years of its operation. The business will be expected of high gains and allowing it for possible area expansion...”- BPES-07</p> <p>“Financial ratios for brownies business are effective indicators of a company’s performance. The company's payback period is in 11 months of operations...”- BPES-09</p> <p>“The business will grow a rate of sales in every year by 8% of the business operation. With the strategies of the business and the good quality of the seedlings, there is no doubt that the business will grow someday...”- BPES-10</p>

As seen in the tabular presentation above, there are five rhetorical move structures employed by the writers and it was evident in the Business Plan Executive Summary in the year 2019-2022. The moves were observed namely Introduction- Purpose- Method- Product- Conclusion.

The first move, which is the introduction, clearly introduces the context of the summary. Along with this, it describes the motives of the report, and the primary context or provides a brief description of the business presented. Yet, the introduction move is only aimed at presenting the generalization and stating the overall explanation of the whole summary such as introducing a certain product or service. And it aims to orient and convince readers about the business. The purpose move states the interest and the aims of the content, methods that claim the procedures and describe the subjects, the product that presents the report and the findings, and the conclusion that should interpret the results presented.

Introduction. The introduction move is seen on the identified corpora. In the corpora, there are terms or words stated that present a description of the business. The introduction move expressed generally the background information about the business or the product. This move establishes a foundation for the main idea to be explored further and it includes details about the company, its unique selling points, and/or the nature of the business.

Primarily, the corpora below describe the motives of the product or the type of business it will be. In the description given by the writers about the business, the writer highlighted the interest of the business at the beginning of the summary which is to provide quality and trustworthy services to the target market. It mainly presented how the business will meet the needs of its target customer and discussed the competitive edge it has. Demonstrated below is the sample statement that these descriptions were found in the corpora that were analyzed.

This printing service or printing shop will focus on reducing a printing price structure, for printing presses and graphic art design. It depends on giving a service to students who need a quality and trustworthy printing shop and will offer services not available in the market... (BPES-02)

After that, the next corpora are from business plan executive summary number three in which it stated an example statement of the introduction move. Aside from giving a description, part of the first move is stating the specificity of the business or product that the company wants to stand out and offer such as emphasizing what their business offers by stating it offers hair and nail spa, hair color, and rebond, and make-up and pinpointing what the customers can expect from their services.

This salon business offers hair rebond, hair color, make-up, and nail spa in the market. The business will be located at Brgy Gabuyan, Kapalong, Davao del Norte... (BPES-03)

Moreover, in BPES07 the statement shows a description of what kind of products they can offer to their customers. Also, stating what makes their shop unique and its edge over other coffee shops, which have a mini library for those customers who want to read books while waiting for their orders, helps the shop to promote the products it offers. It specifies the kind of drinks as well it serves and

presents an option to enjoy their drinks.

The first-ever coffee shop with a mini library in the municipality of Kapalong. It serves various kinds of hot and cold drinks such as coffees, lattes, tea, milk, and smoothies. Also, it will be available for dine-in and take-out orders... (BPES-07)

Thereafter, the corpora had belonged to the statement of business plan executive summary number four. The writer started the summary by incorporating details that will grab the attention of the customers by stating it is a store that offers crisp and succulent moist and tasty meat roasted suckling pig that easily falls off the bones and by the statement of baked brownies that are nutritious, fudge, and delicious for everyone.

It is a store that offers crisp and succulent moist and tasty meat roasted suckling pig that easily falls off the bones and will provide satisfaction to the needs of the consumers at affordable prices... (BPES-04)

Aside from that, corpora number nine includes details of the product which is a description of what kind of brownies it offers to its customers. It stated the options as well on its flavors to choose from and included the benefits that the customers can gain from buying these brownies. The proponents of this business gave a healthy option by making customers choose either an ordinary brownie or low-carb brownies.

This product produces baked brownies that are nutritious, fudge, and delicious for everyone. Customers can choose brownies from a variety of flavors and categories. These brownies are not just ordinary brownies from other stores because the customer can choose between regular and low-carb brownies...(BPES-09)

Purpose. The second move was the purpose move of the corpora being analyzed. This move pertains to a section of the summary in which the primary objective and intention of the report were communicated. It focuses on the statement stated by the writers to the fundamental belief or goals and objectives that have been written. In these corpora, the proponents mentioned the real aims and goals of each business by using such terms and words to easily identify the objectives that been wanted to achieve.

Accordingly, for the purpose section of the corpora, one shows stipulated. So, to inform the readers about the goals of the business or the product, the writer employed the words aims which means that they have a desired intention on what a business wanted to achieve. Further, in the phrases the business aims to provide food that has premium quality was the stated desire meanwhile to ensure customer satisfaction was the thing that been wanted to achieve.

The business aims to provide food that has premium quality to ensure customer satisfaction. The product has a twist and innovation, and the pricing to compete in the market...(BPES-01)

Meanwhile, in corpora three, the writer also employed the words aims in which it stands that the salon aims to be the number one salon in the locality and has the intention of offering job opportunities to the people. The purpose has been stated by stating the desires of the proponents that they wanted in the future and this statement has clearly stipulated its intention.

The salon aims to be the number one salon in the locality and wants to provide job opportunities to the people who are skilled and willing to work... (BPES-03)

Besides, in corpora, number five it effectively communicated its objective using the phrase “envisions to” which means having an intention to work out such a situation in the future. The writer used the terms to help readers anticipate a vision and goal such as stating that the business envisions offering quality and affordable gas service. The intention of giving a quality product to the customers was the purpose and a goal that had been desired by the proponents. The statement stipulated below was the sample of the purpose moves in the corpora that have been analyzed.

This business envisions offering quality and affordable gas service with facilities and systems powered by advanced technology. And, its goals and objectives of this business are to provide excellent service to valued customers...(BPES-05)

Along with this, corpora number ten communicated its objective using the phrase as well “envisions to”. The statement stipulated below anticipated its goals by stating that the business envisions being a competitive seedling business and a successful provider of seedlings. The intention of being a high-quality seedlings provider in the Municipality became the goal and the purpose of establishing this business.

The business envisions being a competitive seedling business and a successful provider of seedlings in the Municipality of Kapalong. The goal is to provide good quality seedlings to the potential customers to satisfy their farm needs...(BPES-10)

Lastly, in corpora number nine, the statement communicated its purpose using the phrase “aspire to” which means to seek ambitiously to achieve the goal of the business and its success. In this corpus, the writer utilized the term to be able to indicate the intention of the business to the readers of the summary. Moreover, the purpose move of the corpora shows determination and clear ambition to ensure that the readers will grasp the objective that is set by its proponents.

The brownie product aspires to promote top-quality taste to individuals. It aims to provide its vision and communication to customers to exceed their expectations and to produce healthy snacks that taste great...(BPES-09)

Method. Following that, the examples below are under the method move of the analyzed corpora. It stated that there are outlined steps and sequential actions that have been followed by the writers to ensure that they can successfully operate within a legal framework such as obtaining permits, licenses, and registrations, and have operational efficiency and quality assurance to sustain their business venture.

Correspondingly, the corpora number eight according to the statements included in the method move, provides an essential process to be taken by the proponents for the success of the business or products, collecting information through surveys with its questionnaires helps to determine the considerations in the business venture. The statements given below are the corpora that have been analyzed.

The proponents surveyed questionnaires from establishments and individuals as they would be the future target market the proponents provided good enough consideration on possible variables that could influence the business operations...(BPES-08)

Thereafter, corpora number nine, enabled to collection of the data needed, the process that has been through by the proponents of this corpora was by utilizing the form-based survey questionnaires to determine the market demand that the proponents needed for their business. It was their essential process to collect information.

The proponents utilized form-based survey questionnaires to get more detailed information about the potential customers. To determine the market demand of the said areas, 381 individual samples from 7, 916 households were taken using quota sampling...(BPES-09)

After that, corpora number eleven, the essential process taken by the proponents of this corpora to be able to determine the pulse of their customers was using survey questionnaires. It was their initial step to their business to learn if their skimming pricing method was effective or not for the customers. The statements given below are the corpora that have been analyzed.

The business will use the skimming pricing method in which a firm charges a high initial price and then gradually lowers the price to attract more price-sensitive customers. The proponents will use a survey questionnaire to determine the pulse of the customers...(BPES-11)

After that, Corpora Number One outlines its process of operation by collecting and submitting the requirements that the business must comply with to ensure the legitimacy of the business and secure the license to operate. It was the process that was been through by the proponent and that was the method that was considered by the writers.

As part of the legal obligation, the business will submit all the requirements set by the government to operate the business legally. The business will secure a license to operate for the legitimacy of the business and will have a legal form of ownership as a sole proprietorship type of business... (BPES-01)

Finally, the last corpora of the method move is the business plan executive summary number three. The sample statement below presents a method or process on how the proponents can determine the internal and external factors that can influence the entire business. To assess, the writers follow steps such as the swot analysis process to gather the essential information that a reader can gain to understand the system, operation, and nature of the business venture.

To know the internal and external factors that affect the business, a SWOT analysis was made to evaluate business strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, to formulate good and new strategies for the benefit of the business... (BPES-03)

Product. The writers crafted an executive summary that can be labeled as the resulting move of the analyzed corpora. A product intends to reveal the findings of the entire document. However, the results presented in this corpus are results about the possible outcome of the business in the future and the findings of the survey conducted. This allows the business to learn a strategy, understand the operations, and decide a future direction for the business opportunities.

Afterward, corpora 4 stated below, presented a finding from a survey conducted. The result shown below is the result of the conducted online survey among the selected respondents. The proponents of this business were able to gather the total number of households within the Barangay and able to determine the size of the population it consisted of. Also, the proponents were able to identify the percentage of the customers who prefer to buy the product.

After the proponents conducted an online survey among the selected respondents of Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The total number of households within the barangay is 3,949 represented by 100 respondents, and it showed that 94% of the respondents prefer to avail the cochinillo... (BPES-04)

Secondly, Corpora Eight stated its findings from the survey conducted by the proponents of this business. Based on the results of the survey, the proponents were able to determine positive feedback from their respondents. They have gathered data as well for their target market needed to operate their business and they found out that many buyers are looking for alternatives in terms of foods, materials, and/or daily groceries.

The result of the survey positively shows that more consumers and businesses looking for other alternatives to be used for their daily groceries, food, packaging materials, and more. Based on the survey, the data showed the capacity of the target market to avail the products...(BPES-08)

Beyond that, demonstrated below is the corpora number seven. In which its findings were based on the survey and responses of their target market. By presenting percentages as the basis, the results of the survey make clear, wherein 30% will not avail of the product and 70% who remain as the potential market.

The result shows that 30% of the respondents being surveyed prefer not to avail services from coffee shop business and rather to have their instant coffee at home, while the remaining 70% is the potential market who will avail the business...(BPES-07)

Following that, in corpora number eleven, the results were been presented through percentages. The proponents were able to gather the data needed for their business based on the findings of their survey conducted. Further, in their 100 respondents, there are only 4% who do not want to avail meanwhile, there are 96% who preferred to avail.

As a result of the survey conducted to over 100 respondents, 96% of them preferred to avail surprises and 4% of them do not want to avail...(BPES-11)

Eventually, in the final corpora number six under this product move, the proponents presented their results by showing the percentage as well according to the findings of their survey. The proponents were able to determine how many customers and respondents did not want to experience their services. Aside from that, they have also had a chance to know the feedback and expectations from their customers regarding their delivery services.

The result shows that the majority of the customers are mostly students and some senior citizens. And according to the survey, 4% of the 1000 respondents were not avail of the services and 96% were positive about availing the delivery services...(BPES-06)

Conclusion. The conclusion move serves as an outline for growth opportunities in the future of the business. It refers to the implication of the writers on what could be a suggestion they wanted to make and plan an action based on the suggested results from the procedures conducted in the business. Moreover, the proponents of the business will conclude a potential guideline for future actions and create a strategic recommendation for the business venture.

Primarily, the sample from corpora number two presented a strategic recommendation on how the business will determine its growth opportunities. The writers are making suggestions like establishing strategies by stating what should be developed for the customers and crafting plans for future huge businesses. This corpus ends up providing recommendations based on the results of the method they have been through.

This business must develop unique styles that provide customers with various ways to create business stationery. Also, the company should develop plans to negotiate deals with big businesses... (BPES-02)

Additionally, the sample corpora number eight under conclusion move presented a strategic recommendation as well to their business. The writers recommended that having good management between their financial statements will help their business to measure performance and stability. Moreover, it concludes as well that the business will have a payback period for the next two years.

All business transactions should be properly recorded to track the smooth running business. Good management of financial statements is important in the business to evaluate and measure the performance and stability of the business. The business payback period is 2 years and 1 month...(BPES-08)

Additionally, corpora number seven gave an implication for establishing a vision that the business and its proponents wanted to achieve in the long run. The proponents concluded that from four to five years of operation, the business was expected to have a high gain and high returns and envision to have a possibility of business expansion in the future.

After all the computation analysis of the net profit of this Cafe business, the return on investment will be from 4 to 5 years of its operation. The business will be expected of high gains and allow it for possible area expansion...(BPES-07)

Afterward, corpora number nine envisions anticipating a return on investment for the next eleven months of operation. This concludes that the proponents are building a hopeful vision for their business even in a short period. Further, being hopeful for growth opportunities for their business attracts an effective and efficient company performance.

Financial ratios for brownies business are effective indicators of a company's performance. The company's payback period is in 11 months of operations...(BPES-09)

Also, in the final corpora ten, the proponents of this business were establishing a vision for the growth of rate sales in every year of operation. Recommending good strategies that can benefit their business was the implication of its proponents in this business. Furthermore, believing in their product that it can gain growth opportunities in the future was their way to lead towards success.

The business will grow a rate of sales in every year by 8% of the business operation. With the strategies of the business and the good quality of the seedlings, there is no doubt that the business will grow someday...(BPES-10)

Research Question 2: What are the common structures found in business plan executive summaries from the year 2019-2022?

The structure is important that a writer of an executive summary must learn to effectively communicate the key information or ideas,

facilitate decision-making, strengthen an argument, and enhance the readability of the report to the readers. Having an organized format of an executive summary ensures that the intended purpose of the document provides a clear overview of the content and highlights the essential data in a logical sequence.

Thereafter, discourse can have a variety of meanings, but in general terms, it refers to communication, discussion, or a specific approach to addressing and recognizing a topic or an issue. In this study, rhetorical structure concepts are a focus of the analysis. Moreover, format, structures, and moves were included which represent a particular communicative function.

In Table 2, the first column presents the move structures to identify the common move structures employed in the business plan executive summary. Then the last column was the frequency which will determine the dominant move observed in the corpora. With this, there are three dominant moves observed in the corpora.

Table 2. *Frequency of Moves Observed in the Business Plan Executive Summary*

<i>Move Structure</i>	<i>Frequency (n=21)</i>
I-P-M-Pr-C	14
I-M-Pr-C	5
I-P-M-Pr	2

Interestingly, it was observed that there are three (3) move structures present in the corpus of business plan executive summary. Three dominant moves have been noticed namely Introduction- Purpose- Method- Product- Conclusion, Introduction-Method- Product-Conclusion, and Introduction- Purpose- Method- Product. Meanwhile, frequency pertains to the structure of the moves that occur and are observed in the business plan executive summary (corpora). Aside from that, in the 21 total number of corpora, I-P-M-Pr-C observed that they have 14 frequencies of moves, the I-M-Pr-C structure has five (5) frequencies of moves, and the I-P-M-Pr has two (2) frequency observed.

However, Table 2.1 presents the first common structure found in the Business Plan Executive Summary from the year 2019-2022. To clearly understand, the first column presents the common structure. It was observed that the first common move structure which is the Introduction (I)- Purpose(P)- Method(M)- Product (Pr)-Conclusion (C). The second column presents the sample statements in an executive summary of a business plan. The code BPES which stands for business plan executive summary to be followed by number stands as a code for each corpus. The following excerpts below are from the three dominant moves and have been presented for reference.

I-P-M-Pr-C. The first dominant move was found in a business plan executive summary. In this structure, the information is logically sequenced, and the key information emphasizes the relevance and significance of the business or the product. Moreover, the introduction, purpose, method, product, and conclusion structure were clearly outlined and described as what a business will cover and all about. With the complete and arranged paragraphs and sections in a coherent sequence, it allows the reader to follow the overview of the business effortlessly.

Correspondingly, the first move presented below is a logical sequence which means that it becomes clear upon organizing its text and it has an organizational pattern that can be followed by the readers for them to draw a connection to the text. In addition to this, the information provided will be more interesting because readers can immediately understand the ideas that the writer presented. Furthermore, the Corpora that consisted of the first move structure are the corpora that are easy to follow, also, this first move structure in the business plan executive summary helps to guide the reader through the thoughts and argument of the writer.

The initial sentences introduce the type of business (a printing shop) and its primary focus which is to reduce a printing price structure for printing presses and graphic art design. It highlights the target customer (students) base in need of quality and trustworthy printing services. This segment provides a background of the business.

Table 2.1. *I-P-M-Pr-C Structure found in the Business Plan Executive Summary from the year 2019-2022*

<i>Move Structure</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
I-P-M-Pr-C	<p>“This printing service or printing shop will focus on reducing a printing price structure, for printing presses and graphic art design. It derives from giving a service to students who need a quality and trustworthy printing shop (Introduction). Thus, it intends to establish and operate a printing shop with services costing significantly the same prices as its competitors while supplying good quality (Purpose). The proponents have undertaken relevant surveys and interviews to understand what the business will be like and how to sustain itself in the market (Method). It assumed that income generated will increase by 5% in year 2, 8% in year 3, and 12% in year 5 (Product). This business must develop unique styles that provide customers with various ways to create business stationery. Also, the company should develop plans to negotiate deals with big businesses (Conclusion)”. BPES-02</p> <p>“This product produces baked brownies that are nutritious, fudge, and delicious for everyone. Customers can choose brownies from a variety of flavors and categories. These brownies are not just ordinary brownies from other stores because the customer can choose between regular and low-carb brownies (Introduction). The brownie product aspires to promote top-quality taste to individuals. It aims to provide its vision and communication to customers to exceed their expectations and to produce</p>

healthy snacks that taste great (Purpose). To determine the market demand of the said areas, 381 individual samples from 7,916 households were taken using quota sampling (Method). The poll found that in yummy brownies, the majority of respondents are enthusiastic about ideas of low-carb brownies (Product). Financial ratios for brownies business are effective indicators of a company's performance. The company's payback period is in 11 months of operation (Conclusion)". BPES-09

"The first ever coffee shop with mini library in the municipality of Kapalong. It serves various kinds of hot and cold drinks such as coffees, lattes, tea, milk, and smoothies. Also, it will be available for dine-in and take-out orders (Introduction). The Cafe shop business aims to be the number one Coffee shop in the municipality for the next 5 years (Purpose). To gather data to begin this Cafe, the proponents conducted an online survey among the respondents within the municipality of Kapalong., wherein there are total population of 21,327 and the total number of households was 4,847(Method). The result shows that 30% of the respondents being surveyed prefer not to avail services from the coffee shop business and rather to have their instant coffee at home, while the remaining 70% is the potential market who will avail the business (Product). After all the computation analysis of the net profit of this Cafe business, the return on investment will be from 4 to 5 years of its operation. The business will be expected of high gains and allow it for possible area expansion (Conclusion)". BPES-07

The third sentence outlines the proponents' intention to establish and operate a printing shop with competitive pricing while sustaining good quality. This move focuses on the purpose and competitive positioning of the business. Thus, it intends to establish and operate a printing shop with services costing significantly the same prices as its competitors without compromising its quality. The fourth sentence describes the methodology used by the proponents to understand the market and ensure business sustainability. This section emphasizes the use of surveys and interviews. Proponents have undertaken relevant surveys and interviews to be able to understand what the business will be like and how to sustain it in the market.

In the fifth sentence, it discusses the expected financial outcomes, indicating projected income growth over several years. This move presents the results of the business analysis where it is assumed that the income generated will increase by 5% in year 2, 8% in year 3, and 12% in year 5. The final sentences outline the strategies for the business to differentiate itself and negotiate with large companies. This segment serves as the conclusion summarizing strategic plans for long-term success. Moreover, this business must develop unique styles that provide customers with various ways to create business stationery. The corpora demonstrated below ensure that the proposal is clear and logically organized, making it easy for readers to understand the business concept, intentions, methodology, findings, and plans.

This printing service or printing shop will focus on reducing a printing price structure, for printing presses and graphic art design. It derives from giving a service to students who need a quality and trustworthy printing shop (Introduction). Thus, it intends to establish and operate a printing shop with services costing significantly the same prices as its competitors while supplying good quality (Purpose). The proponents have undertaken relevant surveys and interviews to understand what the business will be like and how to sustain itself in the market (Method). It assumed that income generated will increase by 5% in year 2, 8% in year 3, and 12% in year 5 (Product). This business must develop unique styles that provide customers with various ways to create business stationery. Also, the company should develop plans to negotiate deals with big businesses (Conclusion). (BPES-02)

Moreover, in the second sample statement on the same move structure, the first three sentences introduce the product (baked brownies) and highlight its unique features, such as being nutritious, fudge, and delicious, with a variety of flavors and categories. The fourth and fifth sentences outline the product's aspiration to promote top-quality taste and its vision to provide great-tasting, healthy snacks that exceed customer expectations. The sixth sentence describes the method used to determine market demand, specifying that 381 individual samples from 7,916 households were taken using quota sampling. The seventh sentence presents the results of the survey, indicating that most respondents are enthusiastic about the idea of low-carb brownies. The eighth sentence discusses the financial ratios as indicators of company performance, and it mentions that the company's payback period is within 11 months of operation. This move provides a conclusion about the business's financial viability. The corpora presented below make certain that the proposal is coherent and logically organized, making it easy for readers to grasp the business concept, intentions, methodology, findings, and strategic plans.

This product produces baked brownies that are nutritious, fudge, and delicious for everyone. Customers can choose brownies from a variety of flavors and categories. These brownies are not just ordinary brownies from other stores because the customer can choose between regular and low-carb brownies (Introduction). The brownie product aspires to promote top-quality taste to individuals. It aims to provide its vision and communication to customers to exceed their expectations and to produce healthy snacks that taste great (Purpose). To determine the market demand of the said areas, 381 individual samples from 7,916 households were taken using quota sampling (Method). The poll found that in yummy brownies, the majority of respondents are enthusiastic about ideas of low-carb brownies (Product). Financial ratios for brownies business are effective indicators of a company's performance. The company's payback period is in 11 months of operation (Conclusion). (BPES-09)

As such, in the third sample statements on the same move structure, the first three sentences introduce the business concept (a coffee shop with a mini library) and describe the variety of drinks it will serve (coffees, lattes, tea, milk, and smoothies). Aside from that, the fourth sentence outlines the business aim, which is to become the number one coffee shop in the municipality within the next five years. Meanwhile, the fifth sentence describes the methodology used to gather data for starting the cafe, specifying that an online survey was conducted among the respondents within the municipality, detailing the population and number of households. The sixth sentence

presents the results of the survey, indicating that 30% of respondents prefer not to use the coffee shop services and would rather have instant coffee at home, while 70% represent the potential market for the business. Finally, the last sentences discuss the financial analysis, stating that the return on investment will be within 4 to 5 years of operation, and the business is expected to have high gains, allowing for possible area expansion. These corpora stipulated below ascertain that the proposal is clear and logically organized, making it easy for readers to understand the business concept, goals, research methodology, findings, and financial projections.

The first-ever coffee shop with a mini library in the municipality of Kapalong. It serves various kinds of hot and cold drinks such as coffees, lattes, tea, milk, and smoothies. Also, it will be available for dine-in and take-out orders (Introduction). The Cafe shop business aims to be the number one Coffee shop in the municipality for the next 5 years (Purpose). To gather data to begin this Cafe, the proponents conducted an online survey among the respondents within the municipality of Kapalong., wherein there are total population of 21,327 and the total number of households was 4,847 (Method). The result shows that 30% of the respondents being surveyed prefer not to avail services from the coffee shop business and rather to have their instant coffee at home, while the remaining 70% is the potential market who will avail the business (Product). After all the computation analysis of the net profit of this Cafe business, the return on investment will be from 4 to 5 years of its operation. The business will be expected of high gains and allow it for possible area expansion (Conclusion). (BPES-07)

Table 2.2 presents the I-M-Pr-C structure found in the Business Plan Executive Summary from the year 2019-2022. To clearly understand, the first column presents the common structure. It was observed that there is another common structure which is the Introduction- Method- Product- Conclusion. The second column presents the sample statements in an executive summary of a business plan. The code BPES which stands for business plan executive summary to be followed by a number stands as a code for each corpus. The following excerpts below are from the three dominant moves and have been presented for reference.

M-Pr-C. The second dominant move structure is found in a business plan executive summary. In these corpora, the structure of the information was not sequentially ordered and followed by the writer. The purpose move was not stated, and the main aim or goal of the summary was not emphasized by the writer. This deviation results in a lack of coherence and hinders a clear reader's understanding of the document. What is more, the lack of sequence will make it challenging for the reader to follow the flow of ideas and understand the overall message of the executive summary.

Apart from that, the second move structure below was observed to have a missing important move in the summary which is the purpose move. In these corpora, the goals and objectives that been wanted to achieve by the proponents are not that clearly stated which makes the researcher and other readers confused about what the Business or product tries to attain. Further, the identified corpora below are samples of a move structure that does not have a purpose.

Primarily, it is the first identified corpora under this move structure. As it introduces the product that the business established and presented, writers promote the kind of industry that it will be in the future, and it has been stated in the first sentence of the corpora. The writer directly pointed out the process or method that this product will get through in a way of conducting surveys to recognize the variables in business operations. Aside from that, the result of the survey is presented which shows the capacity of the product to cater to a huge group of individuals. The writer also concluded with a strategic recommendation to maintain the stability of the business itself. The statements below are the corpora that have been analyzed.

Table 2.2. I-M-Pr-C structure found in the Business Plan Executive Summary from the year 2019-2022

<i>Move Structure</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
I-M-Pr-C	<p>“This is a retailer of Eco-packaging products for different business establishment consumers and other different industries that will carry a sustainable future and customer satisfaction (Introduction). The proponents surveyed questionnaires from establishments and individuals as they would be the future target market the proponents provided good enough consideration of possible variables that could influence the business operations (Method). The result of the survey positively shows that more consumers and businesses looking for other alternatives to be used for their daily groceries, food, packaging materials, and more. Based on the survey, the data showed the capacity of the target market to avail the products (Product). All business transactions should be properly recorded to track the smooth running business. Good management of financial statements is important in the business to evaluate and measure the performance and stability of the business. The business payback period is 2 years and 1 month (Conclusion)”. BPES-08</p> <p>“The first vegetable juice is located at Sto.Tomas, Davao del Norte. It will offer three flavors chayote, carrots, and cucumber that help individuals to be healthier by drinking vegetables (Introduction). The proponents conducted a face-to-face survey among the constituents of Barangay Tibal-og with a stated total population of 51,071 and 150 respondents were extracted as a sample population (Method). Based on the results, there were 8.1% of senior citizens, 26.2% of students, 15.4% of fish vendors, and 50.1% of employed will avail of fresh vegetable juice (Product). The fresh vegetable juice is a good business to support the healthy lifestyle of the customers. The business will achieve its payback period in the year 1 and 3 months upon the computation, and that business has positive results every year of the operation (Conclusion)”. BPES-19</p> <p>“The inland resort is a business structure offering recreational services and recreational activities. The resort is providing the demand of the people to unwind and visit such beautiful places. The inland resort will be erected at Capungagan, Kapalong, Davao del Norte (Introduction). The management will be employing 20 personnel, which includes 1 Manager, 1 HR Manager, 2 Front Desks in charge, 1 pool Attendant, 3 Lifeguards, and other significant members of the management to operate by the</p>

standards of the business (Method). The capitalization requirement is four million pesos and will be equally contributed by the partners. The business financial results indicate that there will be a payback period for the next three years (Product). All business transactions will be carefully recorded to ensure that the entire operation runs smoothly. Financial statement management is vital in the business for evaluating and measuring the company’s success and stability (Conclusion)”. BPES-17

This is a retailer of Eco-packaging products for different business establishments consumers, and other different industries that will carry a sustainable future and customer satisfaction (Introduction). The proponents surveyed questionnaires from establishments and individuals as they would be the future target market the proponents provided good enough consideration of possible variables that could influence the business operations (Method). The result of the survey positively shows that more consumers and businesses looking for other alternatives to be used for their daily groceries, food, packaging materials, and more. Based on the survey, the data showed the capacity of the target market to avail the products (Product). All business transactions should be properly recorded to track the smooth running business. Good management of financial statements is important in the business to evaluate and measure the performance and stability of the business. The business payback period is 2 years and 1 month (Conclusion). (BPES-08)

Secondly, with the same move structure presented above, the business was been introduced by promoting the product with its delicious flavors which makes the product unique. By stating the setting of the business, it can be able to gather customers. Meanwhile, in the third line of the summary, it stated below the survey was conducted to gather the exact total population and some respondents to participate in the survey. Therefore, based on its result, certain identified individuals are willing to avail their product. For the last two sentences of the corpora, writers conclude a vision that the business will attain its payback for even a year of operation.

The first vegetable juice is located at Sto.Tomas, Davao del Norte. It will offer three flavors chayote, carrots, and cucumber that help individuals to be healthier by drinking vegetables (Introduction). The proponents conducted a face-to-face survey among the constituents of Barangay Tibal-og with a stated total population of 51,071 and 150 respondents were extracted as a sample population (Method). Based on the results, there were 8.1% of senior citizens, 26.2% of students, 15.4% of fish vendors, and 50.1% of employed will avail of fresh vegetable juice (Product). The fresh vegetable juice is a good business to support the healthy lifestyle of the customers. The business will achieve its payback period in the years 1 and 3 months upon the computation, and that business has positive results every year of the operation (Conclusion). (BPES-19)

As such, in the third statement in the second move structure, the summary was introduced as a way of offering the services and activities that can be available to the customers. Following sequential action like the standard on how the business will be managed and composed of personnel is by the method move that has been presented. Also, the result is the possible outcomes of the business in the long run of operation. Eventually, the summary was concluded by the writer by giving strategic recommendations about the importance of recorded business transactions and financial statement management. Stipulated below are the corpora that have been analyzed.

The inland resort is a business structure offering recreational services and recreational activities. The resort is providing the demand of the people to unwind and visit such beautiful places. The inland resort will be erected at Capungagan, Kapalong, Davao del Norte (Introduction). The management will be employing 20 personnel, which includes 1 Manager, 1 HR Manager, 2 Front Desks in charge, 1 pool Attendant, 3 Lifeguards, and other significant members of the management to operate by the standards of the business (Method). The capitalization requirement is four million pesos and will be equally contributed by the partners. The business financial results indicate that there will be a payback period for the next three years (Product). All business transactions will be carefully recorded to ensure that the entire operation runs smoothly. Financial statement management is vital in the business for evaluating and measuring the company’s success and stability (Conclusion). (BPES-17)

As such, table 2.3 presents the I-P-M-Pr structure found in the Business Plan Executive Summary from the year 2019-2022. To clearly understand, the first column presents the common structure. It was observed that there is a last common move structure which is the Introduction- Purpose- Method and Product. The second column presents the sample statements in an executive summary of a business plan. The code BPES which stands for business plan executive summary to be followed by a number stands as a code for each corpus. The following excerpts below are from the three dominant moves and have been presented for reference.

Table 2.3. I-P-M-Pr Structure found in the Business Plan Executive Summary from the year 2019-2022

Move Structure	Sample Statement
I-P- M- Pr	<p>“The Gas station is a new venture fuel station in the area of San Isidro that offers fuel products. It is owned and operated by a partnership which will be composed of five individuals. It is located along the highway and the target market will be the people who have a vehicle (Introduction). This business envisions offering quality and affordable gas service with facilities and systems powered by advanced technology. , goals and objectives of this business are to provide excellent service to valued customers (Purpose). The proponents surveyed to acquaint the demand and services using quota sampling to attain the sample population that is necessary for the survey (Method). The survey resulted in positive feedback from the people as the majority of the respondents agreed to avail the services (Product)”. BPES-05</p> <p>“The proposed business is a food business in which rice will be topped with the different toppings offered and placed in a paper bowl, and having a whole meal saves on clean-up time. The business will be located in front of Kapalong Transport Terminal. (Introduction). The business envisions offering affordable and delicious meals to the target customers such as drivers, students,</p>

and other walk-in customers (Purpose). The proponents conducted market research regarding the preferences of the target market. The proponents will look for suppliers for their meat, vegetables, and/or drinks. The proponents will put up 200,000 pesos as start-up capital to operate the business (Method). Further, as a result, the majority of the target market agreed to the proposed business. Also, the results show that in 3 years, the business can have its full amount invested (Product)". BPES-13

P-M-Pr. The third dominant move structure was found in a business plan executive summary. In this move structure, the conclusion move was not presented in the corpora. It shows the absence of clear suggestions, recommendations, and implications at the end part of the summary. The sample statements from the business plan executive summary as the corpora where the I-P-M-Pr found were also presented below.

The third dominant move structure observed has an omission of the essential move which is the conclusion. In these corpora, there are no proper suggestions or there are impermanent strategic recommendations presented by the writers. Moreover, as there are writers who do not end up with their executive summary, it will lead readers to confusion about the potential guidelines, future actions, and other business strategies that the proponents will plan to anticipate for the business venture.

In the first corpora presented below under the third dominant move structure, it was introduced in the first three sentences the product and services it offers and that appears around to be a gas service. The writer presented as well how the fuel business will be owned and operated by the partnership of individuals. Aside from that, the writer established its vision to offer affordable and quality gas services as set the values and goals of the business. Further, through a survey conducted, it was the step that the proponents engaged to gather data about the preferences and needs of the target market. Positive feedback as the result of the survey was mentioned in the end part of the corpora, which includes the responses favorable to the interest and vision of the business.

The Gas station is a new venture fuel station in the area of San Isidro that offers fuel products. It is owned and operated by a partnership which will be composed of five individuals. It is located along the highway and the target market will be the people who have a vehicle (Introduction). This business envisions offering quality and affordable gas service with facilities and systems powered by advanced technology. , The goals and objectives of this business are to provide excellent service to valued customers (Purpose). The proponents surveyed to acquaint the demand and services using quota sampling to attain the sample population that is necessary for the survey (Method). The survey resulted in positive feedback from the people as the majority of the respondents agreed to avail the services (Product). (BPES-05)

Lastly, in the second statement of this third move structure, it appears that the proponent is introducing a food business that specializes in budget-friendly meals for its customers. The writer proposed its goal and objectives which is to be a go-to option for meals within its target market, and it is an indication of setting a good reputation and presence in the food industry and making their business a reliable option for customers. Additionally, the business undertakes market research including searching for suppliers, identifying the market preferences, and establishing a pricing strategy. Eventually, as a result, the proponent was able to receive good feedback from its respondents indicating a potential success in meeting the needs of the target market.

The proposed business is a food business in which rice will be topped with the different toppings offered and placed in a paper bowl, and having a whole meal saves on clean-up time. The business will be located in front of Kapalong Transport Terminal. (Introduction). The business envisions offering affordable and delicious meals to the target customers such as drivers, students, and other walk-in customers (Purpose). The proponents conducted market research regarding the preferences of the target market. The proponents will look for suppliers for their meat, vegetables, and/or drinks. The proponents will put up 200,000 pesos as start-up capital to operate the business (Method). Further, as a result, the majority of the target market agreed to the proposed business. Also, the results show that in 3 years, the business can have its full amount invested (Product). (BPES-13)

Conclusions

This study has been carried out to light the importance of awareness of the existing move structures and the common move structures employed in business plan executive summaries. If used well, the move structure can be a tool for the development of writing and organizing a business plan executive summary. Learning about the common structures employed in the executive summary was a great tool for writers' awareness. It is important as a reader who reads the executive summary that we are vigilant on how we track and locate the important information to understand the text we read.

Furthermore, rhetorical move structures play a vital role in communicating information. In the business plan executive summary, the presence of move structures was evident. The study of how the introduction of moves provided information about the context of the executive summary was an important aspect. In language teaching, the knowledge of how to initiate and introduce the information helps them to convey the origin of words and languages. It makes them aware of how to know the topic, its motives, and how to connect to your readers. In the executive summary, the introduction move was there where the writers generate background of the report and motives of the summary that can be found.

In addition, the purpose of the move was found to be evident in this inquiry. The utilization of purpose moves which the values, vision, and mission of the business were founded in the business plan executive summary. The knowledge of how the goals and objectives of those writers indicated in the report are attached as a significant move. In language teaching, presenting clear objectives is vital.

Language teachers should establish objectives, and their purpose enables them to anticipate an outcome. In an executive summary of the business plan, it is important to determine the purpose of guiding writers in organizing a summary and to easily identify the interest of the business venture.

Moreover, another move that can be seen in this inquiry was the method move. This move's structure involves the process, procedures, or steps presented in the summary. Future language educators could navigate this move in the field of teaching. Methods help language teachers master the content of their subject and apply the content in a particular context. It cannot be denied that through this move, the learning outcomes will be achieved with the help of strategies and techniques in teaching. The essential aspect of recognizing this move is that it helps to determine the process to be taken for successful outcomes.

Aside from that, another move found in the business plan executive summary was the product move. This move was evident based on the outcome and results from the procedures and processes conducted in the business. In the executive summary, the product move was mostly involved in the findings gathered by the proponents. In language teaching, the product from the assessments, surveys, or evaluations helps to determine the progress itself. Through results, language teachers could be able to plan an intervention, develop strategies, or discover professional development for the benefit of their students. This move can be applied by the language teachers as this reveals the outcomes from the method they have followed, and it helps to decide a future direction for better opportunities.

Another move structure found in the business plan executive summary was the conclusion move. This move pertains to the implication of the summary regarding the vision of the business. For future language educators, this move gives closure and reinforces connections to help learners anticipate their goals for the following discussions. In language teaching, it summarizes the information covered in the lesson. This study reveals that this move was important since it completes the information that a summary should consist of. As the overview of a business plan, it was found to be a source of guidelines, potential actions, and strategic recommendations of the proponents for their businesses.

Furthermore, this inquiry observed three dominant move structures that have been used by writers, I-P-M-Pr-C, I-M-Pr-C, and I-P-M-Pr. These dominant move structures observed are the structures that have been followed by the writers. The first dominant move, which is composed of five moves is logically sequenced in which the information provided by the writers has an organized format that is followed by its readers. Meanwhile, the second move which consisted of four moves omits the purpose section. This move structure was not sequentially ordered and the aims and objectives of the summary were not given by the writers. Finally, for the third move, the writer omits to utilize the conclusion move. This means that the writers show the absence of clear recommendations, guidelines and future actions to be taken by the proponents of the business. In language teaching, following different formats makes a language teacher led to confusion about what to focus on teaching the students. Inconsistent language teaching as well will be experienced as they should view different aspects of the learning arena. In addition, various frameworks in teaching language could put the learners put into the test as students' understanding will be measured across the different formats used. This means that the writers of a business plan must follow a certain framework for writing an executive summary.

In performing this research, it has become clear that as a reader we must be familiar with the important parts or sections of an executive summary to acquire and determine the function and message it tries to communicate. Hopefully, the findings of this study, perhaps, it will contribute some insights into the rhetorical move structures and the common move structure employed in a business plan executive summary. Herewith, it will help everyone to widen their learning on how the business plan writers utilized a move pattern to effectively convey the information of an entire business.

This research study has successfully attained its main objectives which are to examine how move structure was used to attain the information clearly in the executive summary, as well as identify the common move structures employed in the business plan executive summary. Indeed, it has been revealed that after data analysis, information has been presented and explanations have been given about the research of this undertaking. Given that this study was only able to analyze 21 business plan executive summaries, the following recommendations for additional research are being presented.

Initially, since this study was focused on the analysis of rhetorical move structure and common move structure manifested in a business plan executive summary, future research may be pursued in the future. With this, future researchers are encouraged to increase the number of corpora they use for validation. In that way, they can employ the same research methodology or framework in this regard. Since the corpora of this inquiry are from the library, they can gather their corpora from other good offices. As such, the use of the same approach or even exploring other approaches is highly encouraged.

Also, as suggested by future researchers they may conduct another study with the same area of concern but at this time using any mixed approaches different from this study. They may study the same corpora as well on the use of move structures on executive summaries that center on writers' move patterns to convey the overview of the entire business. In that way, the insights and findings to be gathered from these future researchers will lead towards improvement of the writers to gain the attention of the readers of an executive summary.

Considering the results yielded, the researcher recommends that the business plan instructors in the business administration department follow a certain pattern upon writing their executive summary. This is to make the student who writes the business plan executive summary familiar with the structure and vital components of a well-written executive summary. Through this, writers will be able to produce a more coherent summary.

Finally, the findings could be reiterated by future researchers. Even so, if the focus of the same corpora will be changed in other move patterns which are not explored in this study. This could lead to a better or distinct understanding of the business plan executive summary.

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